

Green Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction in Pharmaceutical Industry of Pakistan: The Mediating Role of Intention

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 14, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: February 15, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Green, Transformational, Leadership, Job Satisfaction, Intention</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10666920</p>	<p><i>This study investigates the relationship between Green Transformational Leadership (GTL), job satisfaction (JS), and the mediating role of 'intention' in Pakistan's pharmaceutical industry, within the framework of the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory. The research uncovers that GTL, encompassing environmental consciousness, ethical conduct, and innovation, is a unique organizational resource that shapes employees' intentions towards embracing sustainable practices. A quantitative methodology was adopted to achieve the aims of the study and data were collected through an online survey was used to collect the data (418 valid responses) and SmartPLS structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) was employed to hypothesize a model. The results demonstrate that GTL had little significantly direct effect on JS. This study also found that intention has a full mediation effect between GTL and JS. This study contributes to the literature and body of knowledge in green human resource management and organisational behavior through lens of RBV theory.</i></p>

Introduction

The integration of environmental sustainability into management and organisational ideologies has garnered more attention from academia and industry in recent times. The goal is to minimise the adverse impacts of industrial waste and hazards connected to conventional manufacturing. Academics and interested parties have forced organisations to develop strategic plans that simultaneously tackle social, economic, and environmental goals. Research papers demonstrate that how environmentally conscious computer techniques and information technology may significantly reduce energy use, carbon waste, and disposal procedures in businesses (Sikder, 2023). Consequently, academic focus seems to be shifting from a broad discussion of green business to a more functional discussion of green finance (Akomea-Frimpong, 2022), green leadership (Arici, 2022), and green human resources (Sabokro, 2021).

Organisations are gradually incorporating sustainable practices into their operational procedures in response to the growing environmental concern. Leaders are essential change agents who can help companies adopt and encourage these ethical behaviours (Chams, 2019; Lashitew, 2020). In particular, a key strategy for attaining environmental sustainability is Green Transformational Leadership (GTL), which is defined by the promotion of sustainability-oriented norms and behaviours. GTL in this study, representing leaders that not only encourage and inspire those who work for them, but also inculcate an environmental ethic by their choices and behaviours (Begum S. A., 2022). These leaders encourage environmental responsibility, include environmental issues into the organization's overall aims, and provide an example of sustainability through their behaviour.

Given the importance of GTL in influencing organisational results, it is critical to look into the various ways in which GTL influences workplace dynamics in Pakistan's pharmaceutical sector. In light of this, the goal of this research is to determine how GTL influences employee job satisfaction. A key ration of employees' wellbeing, job satisfaction is frequently associated to dedication, productivity, and plans to leave the organisation. However, little research has been done on the mechanism by which GTL influences job satisfaction. According to this research, "intention" plays a mediating role in this relationship (Conner, 2016). According to our research, GTL may have an impact on employees' intents to participate in and support the company's green activities, which may have a major impact on the job satisfaction of employees of pharmaceutical.

Previous research has shown an elevated relationship between leadership styles and job satisfaction. Additionally, studies pertaining to behaviour have shown that intention plays a mediating role in these relationships (Lu, 2019). However, comparatively few research that examine the mediating role of intention in sustainable environment. To bridge this gap and contribute to the expanding research on sustainability and leadership, this study will examine how GTL enhances job satisfaction while considering intention as a mediating factor (Akram, 2023; Tafvelin, 2019). Comprehending this correlation is anticipated to yield significant perspectives for establishments aiming to elevate employee contentment, therefore augmenting their output, efficiency, and, eventually, their ecological endeavours.

Several scholarly studies have examined the connection between transformative leadership and job satisfaction. However, minimal is currently known about how Green Transformational Leadership (GTL) is specifically used and how it impacts job satisfaction, particularly in Pakistan's pharmaceutical industry. Furthermore, not much is known about how "intention" functions as a mediating element in this relationship. Furthermore, the applicability of Resource-Based View (RBV) theory in this context is not sufficiently addressed in the provided content. With a clearer understanding of the ways in which various organisational and cultural factors interact with GTL to effect job satisfaction, this study aims to close these knowledge gaps.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Role of GTL and JS

Scholars who have an interest in investigating the connection between job satisfaction and leadership have primarily concentrated on the transformational leadership approach (Al-edenat, 2018; Pathak, 2023). Leaders that motivate and enable their followers to put the organization's or community's interests ahead of their own are known as transformational leaders (Tintoré, 2019; Kumar, 2020). Few studies emphasize that historically, transformational leaders have put the needs and values of citizenship ahead of their own. Thus, because it is other-centric, this leadership style offers a suitable foundation for investigation in an environmental setting (Dhiman, 2022; Uchida, 2023).

Scholars recognise that behaviours within organisations contribute significantly to environmental degradation (Mensah, 2019). The effectiveness of environmental programmes depends on the actions of leaders and staff members of organisations. Leaders who understand how to incorporate environmental management into their operational plans recognise the need for an adaptable leadership approach (Tembo, 2021; Sajjad, 2023; Cho, 2021). Researchers have studied how transformational leadership could change behaviours to become more environmentally conscious in order to cause such behavioural changes (Suwanto, 2022). Previous studies support the idea that Green Transformational Leadership (GTL) can improve environmental performance (Priyadarshini C. C., 2023; Maitlo, 2022).

According to recent study, "Green Transformational Leadership" (GTL) refers to the behavioural patterns that leaders display in encouraging their subordinates to achieve environmental goals and exceed predetermined standards of environmental performance (Johnson, 2020). GTL works to create a compelling vision that will motivate followers and enhance their capacity to encourage eco-friendly behaviour within the organisation (Chaturvedi, 2022). With the specific goal of enhancing pro-environmental performance, GTL combines the four pillars of transformational leadership: idealised influence, inspiring motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualised consideration (Robertson, 2018).

Initially, leaders who display idealized impact act as role models for environmentally conscious behaviour, which encourages followers to act in a similar manner. A compelling environmental vision that appeals to followers is crafted by them (Dey, 2022; Robertson, 2018). By doing this, leaders present the company as a responsible operational entity and articulate a vision that sets standards (Krasodomska, 2021; Robertson, 2018). This creates a favourable mental framework in the workers' minds, eliciting their commitment and allegiance. Second, via their zeal and idealism, followers of inspiring motivators are able to surmount psychological and physical obstacles (Allal-Chérif, 2021; Robertson, 2018). They inspire people to engage in pro-environmental actions that go beyond pursuing their own interests (Schiuma, 2022). This gives followers a sense of direction and strengthens their dedication to group objectives (Puni, 2021).

Thirdly, intellectually stimulating leaders encourage their followers to reevaluate current organisational procedures, present creative alternatives, and engage critically with environmental concerns (Singh, 2020). These leaders encourage their followers to challenge preconceived notions and accept and value their differing viewpoints. This encourages followers to feel safe and valued cognitively, which motivates them to go above and beyond their position (Schiuma, 2022). Subsequently by taking individual care into account, leaders develop strong bonds with employees while promoting environmental principles and demonstrating concern for the well-being of followers. They also help them improve their competencies (Sergey, 2020). Followers who exhibit this behaviour feel empowered and proud of themselves, which has a beneficial impact on their performance (Zia, 2023).

GTL has become a significant element for organisations aiming to sustain a competitive edge over time by integrating the compelling features of transformational leadership with an environmental mandate. Research investigations have shown that one important result altered by GTL is job satisfaction. Job satisfaction, or positive emotional responses to one's job and its aspects, is a crucial sign of organizational dedication, productivity, and even staff retention (Hanaysha, 2016). The effect of GTL on job satisfaction can be interpreted through the use of both its inherent characteristics and a more thorough theoretical framework, such as the Resource-Based View (RBV) (Chen, 2022). GTL was proven to have a positive effect on employees' job

satisfaction levels because of their increased involvement and dedication to environmental initiatives (Suliman, 2023). A recent study discovered that GTL promoted employees' commitment to the environment, which in turn promoted job satisfaction (Farooq, 2022). For instance, GTL entails establishing high standards for conducting business in an environmentally conscious approach and recognising and rewarding employees who accomplish thus.

A recent study found that GTL—which is exemplified by traits like setting high standards for environmental performance and leading by example—had a significant impact on employees' satisfaction with their job. The study found that GTL leaders' enthusiasm for environmental sustainability had a favourable effect on employees' interest in their work and commitment to the organization's green goals, which in turn raised the employees' job satisfaction (Suliman, 2023). According to study, employees' shown eco-initiatives were favorably correlated with GTL. When their green leaders acknowledged and valued such activities, the staff members felt that their roles had greater value and fulfillment. They felt that receiving this acknowledgment really increased their level of job satisfaction overall (Robertson J. L., 2013).

GTL leaders inspire and engage their followers by providing a framework of intellectual encouragement, vision, and commitment. They provide work environments where individual ambitions are in line with environmental objectives by endorsing and encouraging sustainable behaviors and raising environmental awareness among their followers (Suliman, 2023). These value-aligned work settings frequently result in higher job satisfaction. Job satisfaction was found to be highly correlated with green human resource management, a process driven by GTL (Agrawal, 2023). In a different study, workers' job satisfaction increased in a green workplace where environmental stewardship was demonstrated by transformational leaders (Singh S. K., 2020).

A recent study draw attention to the possibility of organizations engaging in "green washing," a practice in which leadership-level environmental pledges may not materialize into true greening initiatives. Employee confidence may be eroded as a result of this perceived deception, which would lower JS (Farooq., 2022). Furthermore, GTL's initiatives would at first raise JS, the organization's concentration on environmental sustainability might put employees under undue pressure, which would lower their level of satisfaction. Employees may become frustrated or unsatisfied with the green initiative if they believe it is a diversion from their main job responsibilities (Fernet, 2015).

GTL may encourage employees to be more environmentally conscious, it does not always affect how satisfied they are with their jobs (Chen, The small and medium enterprises' green human resource management and green transformational leadership: A sustainable moderated-mediation practice., 2022). Authors suggested that GTL might not have significant effects by arguing that a variety of factors, including the work environment, rewards, and social ties, drive job satisfaction. It's important to remember, though, that these reported insignificances and possible drawbacks are typically the exception rather than the standard. A large quantity of academic research generally indicates that GTL has a beneficial effect on JS (Farooq., 2022). Whereas GTL generally improves JS, some academic research raises the prospect of modest or even possibly adverse effects. Examining these unfavorable situations can be essential to deepening our comprehension of the complexity of GTL and its complicated impacts on JS.

H1: The GTL significantly effect JS

2.2 Mediating role of Intention

A significant finding from research is that GTL influences workers' intentions and attitudes towards the environment. Employees intend to behave in an environmentally conscious manner when their leaders model this behavior, and when their actions align with their goals, their level of job satisfaction increases (Begum S. A., 2022).

When GTL and job satisfaction were examined, Jabbour et al. (2012) discovered that employees who were affected by GTL had greater job satisfaction levels because they were more involved in and committed to environmental projects. This is consistent with the proposed mediation concept, which holds that GTL shapes employee intentions to engage in environmentally friendly behaviors, hence influencing job satisfaction. The study's findings about the mediational impact of employees' intentions, who showed that leaders might influence environmental intents by integrating sustainability into daily operations and organizational culture. Employees felt more fulfilled and had a sense of purpose because of the leaders' actions and their objectives aligning, which improved job satisfaction.

The RBV theory is used, the indirect relationship that exists between GTL and job satisfaction through intention becomes more complex. Intention, as an internal human resource, is essential to converting GTL impact into satisfaction with work (Begum S. X., 2022). Through influencing employee goals to encourage environmentally conscious behavior, GTL leaders indirectly contribute to a more satisfied workforce. In a similar vein, workers' intentions are greatly influenced by their impression of a leader's environmental policies, which in turn raises job satisfaction. Because of the leaders' eco-friendly actions, norms and standards were defined, which influenced employees' intentions to behave in a similar way and increased workplace satisfaction (Kim, 2017).

Intention is a key mediating factor in the relationship between GTL and job satisfaction, according to study. GTL promotes positive attitudes towards environmentally sustainable behaviour, which in turn influences job satisfaction. This demonstrates how crucial it is to encourage GTL in the workplace in order to foster attitudes and goals that support environmental sustainability and raise employee satisfaction (Priyadarshini C. C., 2023).
H2: The intention mediates the relationship between GTL and JS

Figure 1: Conceptual framework for the study

3.1 Sampling design and data collection

The present study employs a survey approach and is grounded in positivist theory. A framework for explanatory research to investigate causal links between variables has been created by Creswell & Creswell (2017). Additionally, a study model and hypotheses were developed using deductive reasoning, which is consistent with the positivist viewpoint.

A framework involving 418 employees from pharmaceutical organizations operating in Pakistan is developed using a quantitative methodology in the current research. The objective was to investigate how Green Transformational Leadership (GTL) effects job satisfaction. The technique of non-random convenience sampling was used to select participants. To assess the structural and measurement models, SmartPLS (version 3) was utilized for Partial Least Squares (PLS) analysis. The theoretical model was validated through the collection of samples from various pharmaceutical organizations in Pakistan.

The survey questionnaire was given to employees at Martin Dow Pharma, AmarantPharma, Getz Pharma, NabiQasimPharma and Merck Pharma, which are prominent players in the pharmaceutical industry. Data was collected using a convenient sampling technique between August 2023 and December 2023. To determine the appropriate sample size, power analysis was used to follow Hair and colleagues (2017) recommendation for Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Modeling. According to Hair et al. (2019), the sample size should be determined by examining the constructs in the model with the most predictors.

3.2 Demographic profile of the sample

The object of this study was to examine the relationship of GTL, JS and role of intention of employees as a mediator. The data was collected from pharmaceutical organizations working in Pakistan. Questionnaires were distributed among 418 respondents. A convenience sampling technique was adopted to collect the data from employees of Pharma industry. 5-point Likert-type scales used as 1 represented "Strongly Disagree" and 5 described "Strongly Agree". The respondents consisted of 69.90% of males, 28.20% of females and 1.90 others. Age-wise, 93.10% of the respondents range in the age group of 18-40, and 6.90% belong to the age group of 41-60. Majority of the responses received from Getz Pharma (24.60%) and most of the responses submitted by Senior / Assistant manager level (29.90%). Most respondents have a bachelor's level qualification (60.80%), and the majority of respondents fell in the experience bracket of 2-5 years (32.80) and more than 10 years (15.40%). The detailed demographic analysis is as follows:

Table 1: Demographic details

Variables	Responses	Frequency (n=428)	Percentage (%)
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Gender	Male	292	69.90%
	Female	118	28.20%
	Others	8	1.90%
Age	18-30	229	54.80%
	31-40	160	38.30%
	41-50	24	5.70%
	51-60	5	1.20%
	Above 60	0	0%
Organization	Martin Dow	70	16.70%
	Amarant	99	23.70%
	Getz Pharma	103	24.60%
	NabiQasim	62	14.80%
	Merck	84	20.10%
Position	Associate	209	50.00%
	Senior / AM	125	29.90%
	Manager	66	15.80%
	Senior Manager	11	2.60%
	Director / DGM	4	1.00%
	GM / HoD	3	0.70%
Education	Matric	10	2.40%
	Intermediate	79	18.90%
	Bachelor	254	60.80%
	Masters	75	17.90%
Experience with current organization	Less 2	96	23.00%
	2-5	137	32.80%
	6-10	121	28.90%
	11-15	43	10.30%
	16-20	12	2.90%
	Above 20	9	2.20%

3.3 Measures

The selection of measurement scales in this study was based on established literature. To improve clarity, a five-point Likert scale was utilized, which ranged from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 5 (Strongly agree). All measurement items were phrased in a positive manner. The Green Transformational Leadership scale was adapted from Robertson et al. (2018). The Job Satisfaction constructs originated from Crow et al. (2012), and the Intention scale was sourced from Conner et al. (2016).

3.4 Data Analysis

This study utilized structural equation modelling (SEM) with partial least squares (PLS) in Smart PLS 3 was to analyze out data (Ringle et al., 2012). The analysis was done through the two-stage approach i.e., measurement model assessment and structural model assessment, as this approach has advantages on the one-step approach. Measurement model indicates how each construct measures, in order to explain the relationship among variables the structural model will indicate how each of the constructs are related to each other (Hair J. F., Multivariate data analysis., 2019).

4. Empirical results

4.1 Measurement Model

This study used the PLS-SEM technique with the SmartPLS algorithm to evaluate the quality of the measurement model in order to determine the validity and reliability of the analysis. The convergent validity of the measurement model was initially evaluated using common reliability and validity measures in PLS-SEM, including Factor Loadings, Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (Hair et

al., 2017; Latan& Noonan, 2017). Table 2 shows Outer Loadings, Cronbach's alpha, Composite Reliability (CR), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) in order to confirm the constructs' internal consistency.

Table 2: Measurement Model Item Loadings, Composite Reliability (CR) & Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Construct	Items	Loading	Cronbach's alpha	CR	AVE
Green Transformational Leadership	GTL1	0.781	0.959	0.964	0.691
	GTL2	0.801			
	GTL3	0.825			
	GTL4	0.841			
	GTL5	0.819			
	GTL6	0.828			
	GTL7	0.861			
	GTL8	0.855			
	GTL9	0.836			
	GTL10	0.860			
	GTL11	0.839			
	GTL12	0.824			
Intention	INT1	0.775	0.877	0.884	0.669
	INT2	0.794			
	INT3	0.844			
	INT4	0.850			
	INT5	0.825			
Job Satisfaction	JS1	0.754	0.808	0.832	0.515
	JS2	0.773			
	JS3	0.822			
	JS4	0.704			
	JS5	0.684			
	JS6	0.533			

4.2 Fornell-Larcker criterion

Using the Fornell-Larcker criterion, the square root of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for every latent variable was assessed in order to assess discriminant validity. According to this criterion, the square root of AVE for every latent variable must be higher than the correlation it has with other latent variables. Table 3 confirms discriminant validity by demonstrating that each latent variable's square root of AVE actually exceeds its correlation with other latent variables.

Table 3: Discriminant validity using Fornell and Larcker's (1981) criterion.

Construct	GTL	INT	JS
GTL	0.831		
INT	0.758	0.818	
JS	0.367	0.425	0.718

4.3 Evaluation of structural/inner Model

This shows the relationships between constructs and related theories based on existing literature (Hair et al., 2019), our model had direct effects and mediation hypotheses. We utilized 5000 samples of bias corrected bootstrapping 95% confidence intervals to test out direct effect, mediation and moderation hypotheses.

Figure 2: Statistical Model

4.4 Hypothesis Testing

H1 GTL had an insignificant impact on JS ($\beta = .098$, $t = 1.199$, $p = .0231$), GTL had a small effect size (Cohen, 1988) on JS ($F^2 = .006$), so H1 was supported.

GTL was having a positive and significant impact on JS through INT ($\beta = .269$, $t = 2.739$, $p = .006$), so H2 was supported indicating the INT mediation was successful. Sobel's (1982) test revealed that the indirect effect of GTL on JS via INT was significant, therefore H2 was further supported.

Table 4: Direct and Indirect effect – Hypothesis results

Relationship	Estimate	StdDev	T	P	F2
GTL -> JS	0.098	0.078	1.199	0.231	0.006
GTL -> INT	0.775	0.027	28.920	0.000	-
INT -> JS	0.348	0.128	2.707	0.007	0.062
Mediation effect					
GTL -> INT -> JS	0.269	0.098	2.739	0.006	-

4.5 Quality of the Structural Model

The predictive quality of the structural model was measured by the means of Q2. Positive value of Q2 (> 0) is an indication of acceptable / good quality or predictive relevance of the structural model. Chin (1998) marked Q2 as 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 to be poor, average, and strong respectively, see Table 5.

R2 measures the predictive power of the model by indicating the amount of variance explained by the predictors in the outcome variables. Cohen (1988) ranked the R2 values as small ($R^2 = .2$), medium ($R^2 = .5$) and large ($R^2 = .8$). GTL explained a variance of 77.5% ($R^2 = .775$) in INT. INT explained a variance of 47.5% ($R^2 = .475$) in JS.

VIF values beyond 5 are not only indication of pathological collinearity but also an indication of model contamination with common method bias (Hair et al., 2019), as shown in Table 5 that all VIF values were less than 5, so pathological contamination was ruled out indicating further quality of the structural model.

Table 5: *Quality Assessment of the Structural Model*

Outcome Variable	Q Square	R Square	VIF
INT	0.506	0.775	3.478
JS	0.233	0.475	2.185

5. Conclusion and Discussion

This study investigated the mediating role of intention in the relationship between green transformational leadership and job satisfaction. The path coefficient finds significant findings with p-value <0.5 and t-value >2, and it provides empirical evidence for the given hypotheses.

The overall statistical findings of our study support the findings of Tosun (2022) and Al-Swidi (2021) that H1 for green transformational leadership has little or no effect on job satisfaction. Using the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory framework to examine the relationship between Green Transformational Leadership (GTL) and Job Satisfaction (JS) in Pakistan's pharmaceutical industry may help clarify the ways in which organisational resources and leadership behaviours interact to influence worker satisfaction.

Based on the RBV theory, leveraging valuable and distinctive internal resources may provide an organization with a sustained competitive advantage (Shan, 2019). In the framework of GTL, these internal resources can be interpreted as the leadership' cognizance of environmental issues, their expertise in sustainable practices, and their capacity to inspire employees to follow in their footsteps.

The impact of GTL on JS, however, could not be considered very excessive given the characteristics of the pharmaceutical industry and Pakistan's distinct cultural context. Any potential benefits that GTL may have on JS may be countered by stress due to higher expectations regarding environmentally friendly methods, given the high standards of the pharmaceutical sector. From a similar direction, the empirical investigation found that the association between green transformative leadership and JS can be lowered in an atmosphere of job stress (Öğretmenoğlu, 2022; Singh, 2020).

The H2 result showed that the indirect effects of green transformational leadership on job satisfaction are significantly mediated by intention (Hameed, 2022; Tosun, 2022). However, it has been shown that GTL positively affects employees' intentions, attitudes, and behaviours with regard to ecological responsibility. This argument suggests that leaders in the pharmaceutical industry that aggressively promote eco-friendly practices should encourage employees to follow the trend, thus leading to increased JS. The collective direction of Pakistani society must be considered from a cultural standpoint. Here, strong GTL traits in leaders enable them to influence both organisational as well as personal intentions, which can boost job satisfaction by encouraging a sense of shared accountability for accomplishing organisational goals and advancing societal welfare.

In the case of Pakistan's pharmaceutical industry, the effect of GTL on employee objectives related to environmental sustainability may have a significant impact on JS. To fully comprehend this relationship, it is necessary to take into account complex processes, such as incentive structures, corporate cultures, and personal traits.

5.1 Theoretical implication

Considering the research findings, the GTL is significantly impacted the employees' JS in pharmaceutical organizations of Pakistan when the mediation of intention and RBV theory are utilized. To understand the situation detailed dynamics, different behaviors of employees and organizational facets has significant theoretical implications. From an RBV standpoint, it underlines how crucial GTL is as a unique and valuable organizational resource that develops a moral, creative, and ecologically conscious culture. This demonstrates how the capacity of leaders to impart sustainable values can influence employees' "intentional" behavior.

5.2 Practical Implications

In pharmaceutical industry, the relationship of GTL, JS and intention have been important implication for practice. This has illustrated that GTL is playing crucial role while adjusting the behaviors of employees at workplace through increasing job satisfaction of employees. This could be through mediating the intentional behavior of employees. The organizations could initiate to start the leadership development programs that will build more sustainable organizational culture for longer and will contribute to suitability principles.

Organizations must recognize the value of fostering employees' good intentions in order to increase job satisfaction and overall productivity. This can include setting an example of consistent behavior and having open conversations about the value of eco-friendly practices. Due to Pakistan's unique industrial constraints and cultural milieu, customized tactics are even more necessary. In order to ensure the successful execution and favorable outcomes of GTL approaches, leaders must consider the unique demands of the pharmaceutical sector in addition to the customs that are common in Pakistan.

5.3 Limitations and Future Research Directions

Our research study has still some limitations which need to be addressed in future research. Although we had extensively investigated the relationship between GTL, JS and Intention in pharmaceutical industry of Pakistan. First, the Resource-Based View (RBV) framework has been the main focus of study up to this point, which has limited our comprehension of the relationships between possible other organizational processes. Future studies might incorporate a variety of theoretical perspectives that provide a more thorough evaluation.

Furthermore, it could be more thought-provoking to generalize the outcomes due to the cultural and industrial quirks of Pakistan's pharmaceutical sector. Comparative research between industries or cultures may therefore provide more thorough insights. Finally, even if "intention" is only considered as one mediator, a more complex narrative may be revealed by including many spanning mediators. In order to gain a deeper comprehension of the complex connections between GTL and JS, future studies could investigate other plausible mediators, including role ambiguity, work autonomy, and motivation

References

- Agrawal, S. &. (2023). Employee green behavior in hotels: the role of green human resource management, green transformational leadership and value congruence. . *Consumer Behavior in Tourism and Hospitality*, , 18(2), 241-255.
- Akomea-Frimpong, I. A. (2022).A review of studies on green finance of banks, research gaps and future directions. . *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, , 12(4), 1241-1264.
- Akram, H. M. (2023). EXPLORING THE INTERRELATIONSHIP AMONG TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP, DIGITAL ADVERTISING ADOPTION, E-COMMERCE ADOPTION, ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE, FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE, AND GREEN MARKETING INNOVATION: AN INVESTIGATION IN THE POST-COVID ERA.
- Al-edenat, M. (2018).Reinforcing innovation through transformational leadership: mediating role of job satisfaction. . *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, , 31(4), 810-838.
- Allal-Chérif, O. G.-G.-M.-C. (2021). Being an ethical leader during the apocalypse: Lessons from the walking dead to face the COVID-19 crisis. . *Journal of Business Research*, , 133, 354-364.
- Al-Swidi, A. K. (2021). The joint impact of green human resource management, leadership and organizational culture on employees' green behaviour and organisational environmental performance. . *Journal of Cleaner Production*, , 316, 128112.
- Arici, H. E. (2022). Leadership, green innovation, and green creativity: A systematic review. . *The Service Industries Journal*, , 42(5-6), 280-320.
- Asif, M. J. (2019). Linking transformational leadership with nurse-assessed adverse patient outcomes and the quality of care: assessing the role of job satisfaction and structural empowerment. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, , 16(13), 2381.
- Begum, S. A. (2022). Does green transformational leadership lead to green innovation? The role of green thinking and creative process engagement. . *Business Strategy and the Environment*, , 31(1), 580-597.
- Begum, S. X. (2022).Achieving green product and process innovation through green leadership and creative engagement in manufacturing.*Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, , 33(4), 656-674.
- Chams, N. &.-B. (2019). On the importance of sustainable human resource management for the adoption of sustainable development goals. . *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, , 141, 109-122.
- Chaturvedi, P. K. (2022). Investigating the role of celebrity institutional entrepreneur in reducing the attitude-behavior gap in sustainable consumption. . *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, , 33(3), 625-643.
- Chen, Y. S. (2022). The small and medium enterprises' green human resource management and green transformational leadership: A sustainable moderated-mediation practice. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, , 29(5), 1341-1356.
- Chin, W. W. (1998). The partial least squares approach to structural equation modeling, *Mod. Methods Bus. Res.* . 295 (1998) 295–336.
- Cho, M. &. (2021). Customer pressure and restaurant employee green creative behavior: serial mediation effects of restaurant ethical standards and employee green passion. . *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, , 33(12), 4505-4525.

- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioural Sciences*, second ed. *Routledge, New York*.
- Conner, M. A.-M. (2016). Impact of goal priority and goal conflict on the intention–health-behavior relationship: Tests on physical activity and other health behaviors. *Health Psychology*, , 35(9), 1017.
- Çop, S. O. (2021). Achieving environmental sustainability through green transformational leadership policy: Can green team resilience help? *Business Strategy and the Environment*, , 30(1), 671-682. .
- Creswell, J. W. (2017). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. . *Sage publications*.
- Crow, M. S. (2012). Organizational justice and organizational commitment among South Korean police officers: An investigation of job satisfaction as a mediator. . *Policing: an international journal of police strategies & management*.
- Dey, M. B. (2022). Ethical leadership for better sustainable performance: Role of employee values, behavior and ethical climate. . *Journal of Cleaner Production*, , 337, 130527.
- Dhiman, S. G. (2022). Servant Leadership: Profiling Three Exemplars from the Twentieth Century. In *The Palgrave Handbook of Servant Leadership*. . *Cham: Springer International Publishing*, pp. 1-33.
- Farooq, R. Z. (2022). Do green human resource management and self-efficacy facilitate green creativity? A study of luxury hotels and resorts. . *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, , 30(4), 824-845.
- Fernet, C. T. (2015). Transformational leadership and optimal functioning at work: On the mediating role of employees' perceived job characteristics and motivation. . *Work & Stress*, , 29(1), 11-31.
- Fornell, C. &. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. . *Journal of marketing research*, , 18(1), 39-50.
- Hair, J. F. (2019). *Multivariate data analysis*. *Cengage Learning, Hampshire, United Kingdom*.
- Hair, J. F. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European business review*, , 31(1), 2-24.
- Hair, J. H. (2017). An updated and expanded assessment of PLS-SEM in information systems research. . *Industrial management & data systems*, , 117(3), 442-458.
- Hameed, Z. N. (2022). How GHRM is related to green creativity? A moderated mediation model of green transformational leadership and green perceived organizational support. . *International Journal of Manpower*, , 43(3), 595-613.
- Hanaysha, J. (2016). Testing the effects of employee engagement, work environment, and organizational learning on organizational commitment. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, , 229, 289-297.
- Johnson, L. K. (2020). *Effects of Transformational Leadership on Direct Home Healthcare Employee Turnover*. (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University).
- Jöreskog, K. G. (1973). Analysis of covariance structures. In *Multivariate analysis—III* , (pp. 263-285). Academic Press.
- Kim, A. K. (2017). Multilevel influences on voluntary workplace green behavior: Individual differences, leader behavior, and coworker advocacy. . *Journal of management*, , 43(5), 1335-1358.
- Krasodomska, J. S. (2021). Extended external reporting assurance: Current practices and challenges. . *Journal of International Financial Management & Accounting*, , 32(1), 104-142.
- Kumar, V. &. (2020). Happiness and workplace well-being: Transformational leadership and the role of ethical and spiritual values. . *The Palgrave handbook of workplace well-being*, , 1-44.
- Lashitew, A. A. (2020). Inclusive business at the base of the pyramid: The role of embeddedness for enabling social innovations. . *Journal of business ethics*, , 162, 421-448.
- Lu, H. Z. (2019). Job satisfaction among hospital nurses: A literature review. . *International journal of nursing studies*, , 94, 21-31.
- Maitlo, Q. W. (2022). Exploring green creativity: The effects of green transformational leadership, green innovation climate, and green autonomy. . *Frontiers in Psychology*, , 13, 686373.
- Mensah, J. (2019). Sustainable development: Meaning, history, principles, pillars, and implications for human action: Literature review. . *Cogent social sciences*, , 5(1), 1653531.
- Öğretmenoğlu, M. A. (2022). The mediating effects of green organizational citizenship on the relationship between green transformational leadership and green creativity: evidence from hotels. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, , 5(4), 734-751.
- Pathak, D. M. (2023). Examining the inter-relationship between leadership styles, organisational learning capability and job satisfaction: an empirical study of Indian IT companies. . *International Journal of Learning and Change*, , 15(1), 51-69.
- Priyadarshini, C. C. (2023). Achieving organizational environmental citizenship behavior through green transformational leadership: A moderated mediation study. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*.
- Puni, A. H. (2021). The interaction effect of transactional-transformational leadership on employee commitment in a developing country. . *Management Research Review*, , 44(3), 399-417.
- Ringle, C. M. (2012). A critical look at the use of PLS-SEM in MIS quarterly. *MIS Q. Manag. Inf. Syst.*, .36(1).

- Robertson. (2018). The nature, measurement and nomological network of environmentally specific transformational leadership. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 151(4), 961-975.
- Robertson, J. L. (2013). Greening organizations through leaders' influence on employees' pro-environmental behaviors. *Journal of organizational behavior*, 34(2), 176-194.
- Sabokro, M. M. (2021). The effect of green human resources management on corporate social responsibility, green psychological climate and employees' green behavior. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 313, 127963.
- Sajjad, A. E. (2023). Sustainability leadership: An integrative review and conceptual synthesis. *Business Strategy and the Environment*.
- Schiama, G. S. (2022). The transformative leadership compass: six competencies for digital transformation entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 28(5), 1273-1291.
- Sergey, B. B. (2020). Modeling of empathy, emotional intelligence and transformational leadership to the project success. In *Mathematical Modeling and Simulation of Systems: Selected Papers of 14th International Scientific-Practical. Springer International Publishing, Chernihiv, Ukraine* (pp. 209-222).
- Shan, S. L. (2019). Big data analysis adaptation and enterprises' competitive advantages: the perspective of dynamic capability and resource-based theories. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 31(4), 406-420.
- Sikder, A. S. (2023). Leveraging Information Technology for Green IT and Sustainable Development: An Analysis of Environmental Sustainability, Energy Efficiency, and Carbon Footprint Reduction Initiatives.: IT for Green IT and Sustainable Development. *International Journal of Imminent Science & Technology*, 1(1), 48-63.
- Singh, S. K. (2020). Green innovation and environmental performance: The role of green transformational leadership and green human resource management. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 150, 119762.
- Suliman, M. A.-K. (2023). Impact of Green Transformational Leadership on Employees' Environmental Performance in the Hotel Industry Context: Does Green Work Engagement Matter? *Sustainability*, 15(3), 2690.
- Suwanto, S. S. (2022). Effect of Transformational Leadership, Servant Leadership, and Digital Transformation on MSMEs Performance and Work Innovation Capabilities. *CEMJP*, 30(4), 751-762.
- Tafvelin, S. N. (2019). Leading well is a matter of resources: Leader vigour and peer support augments the relationship between transformational leadership and burnout. *Work & Stress*, 33(2), 156-172.
- Teixeira, A. A. (2012). Relationship between green management and environmental training in companies located in Brazil: A theoretical framework and case studies. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 140(1), 318-329.
- Tembo, A. (2021). *Strategies to Sustain Business Operations During Continuous Environmental Change*. (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University).
- Tintoré, M. (2019). Introducing a model of transformational prosocial leadership. *Journal of leadership studies*, 13(3), 15-34.
- Tosun, C. P. (2022). Effects of green transformational leadership on green performance of employees via the mediating role of corporate social responsibility: Reflection from North Cyprus. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 103, 103218.
- Uchida, Y. &. (2023). An Interdependent Approach: Manifestations in Cultural Practices. In *An Interdependent Approach to Happiness and Well-Being. Cham: Springer International Publishing*, pp. 97-128.
- Zia, M. &. (2023). How Mutual Respect in Terms of Recognition and Appraisal Between Leaders and Followers, Along with Empathy and Liking Affect Follower Job Performance and Well-Being: The Complementary Role of Culture.

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